

The Role Of Marine Resources And Fisheries Supervision In Empowering The Community To Control Illegal Fishing In The Riau Islands Province

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to examine the role of Marine and Fishery Resources Supervision in empowering the community to monitor illegal fishing. Indonesia's marine wealth undoubtedly increases the potential for illegal fishing, resulting in losses for the state and society as a result of Indonesia's marine wealth for welfare. Illegal fishing activities cause significant economic harm to the community, particularly in terms of natural damage caused by illegal fishing actors. Using environmentally unfriendly fishing gear As mandated, the Marine and Fishery Resources Supervision Base (PSDKP) has several tasks and functions, including developing a strategic work plan, supervising marine and fishery resources, providing group guidance to the supervisory community (POKMASWAS), and evaluating violation handling. Maintain supervision facilities and infrastructure, plan and develop supervisory vessels, and carry out administrative and household administration of Marine and Fishery Resources Supervision Bases. The limited number of supervisory personnel and infrastructure facilities such as supervisory ships make optimal supervision challenging.

Keywords: *community empowerment; illegal fishing; marine resources and fisheries supervision*

A. Introduction

Indonesia is a country known as a "maritime country," which is a country that has a very wide territorial area that generally consists of various large and small islands that lie in the territory of the country. the largest marine mega-biodiversity in the world. It is recorded that there are 8,500 species of fish, 555 species of seaweed, and 950 species of coral reef biota, which gives Indonesia's oceans enormous potential. Exclusive. Only about 2.01 million km² is land. This shows that Indonesia should have a large potential for fishing resources. With the diversity of Indonesia's maritime potential, including the marine biotechnology industry, deep ocean water, marine tourism, marine energy, marine minerals, shipping, defense, and the maritime industry, it can make a major contribution to the welfare and prosperity of the Indonesian people. Indonesia's natural resources are very abundant and have the potential to provide welfare for the community, including the wealth of Indonesia's seas. Indonesia has a lot of natural resources, but foreign ships often steal fish from Indonesian seas. This is because foreign ships with flags from other countries also steal fish from Indonesian seas. The marine

wealth that Indonesia has certainly raises the potential for illegal fishing, which results in losses for the state and society because of Indonesia's marine wealth for welfare. Illegal fishing actions that are carried out provide a lot of harm to the community's economy, especially in the natural damage caused by illegal fishing actors that use fishing gear that is not environmentally friendly. Apart from being an act of theft, this triggers the destruction of marine ecosystems and results in huge losses. In the eyes of the rest of the world, Indonesia will follow Republic of Indonesia Law No. 17 of 1985 if serious action is needed to carry out the rights and obligations to regulate, manage, and use the national marine wealth for the greatest good of the people.

The Riau Archipelago itself is a large and small island chain with as many as 2,408 islands and an area of 251,810 km², there are islands named about 1,350 and also not named around 1,058 islands. The dominance with an area of ± 241,215 km² or 96% and the other is land with an area of 10,594 km² or 4%. The area of the Riau Archipelago increased by 109.03 from 2010–2011, per fishery production. Several media outlets reported that illegal fishing also often occurs in border areas in Indonesia, so that the number of illegal fishing in the Riau Islands is balanced with fishery production. There are 2,408 islands in the Riau Archipelago, small outer islands bordered by 4 countries namely Vietnam, Cambodia, Malaysia, and Singapore, so the struggle must be carried out as a security guard in the Riau Islands province and the 19 outer islands.

It is necessary to have an effort to eradicate illegal fishing that enters the scope of the waters of the Riau Archipelago, thus disturbing the balance of various sectors in marine waters, a Marine and Fishery Resources Supervision Base (PSDKP) is formed, which oversees carrying out activities by carrying out functions based on the Decree of the Minister of Maritime Affairs and Fisheries. Republic of Indonesia Number: PER.69/PERMEN-KP/2020 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of the Technical Implementation Unit for Supervision of Marine and Fishery Resources. Various efforts have been made by the Marine and Fishery Resources Supervision Base (PSDKP) in eradicating illegal fishing, including one of them by involving the community, which is directly related to the economic losses carried out by unscrupulous individuals or perpetrators of illegal fishing. community monitoring group. It is hoped that the public can report to the PSDKP when they see suspicious movements, such as illegal fishing, especially those using fishing gear that is not good for the aquatic environment.

Definition of Role

A role is something that is played or carried out. The definition of a "role" is an activity that is played or played by a group of people who have a position or status in society or in an organization. or a position in society. A "role" can also be understood as "a person's task or duty", in which means "a person's duty or obligation in a business or job." A person, agency, or organization in an event Role is a dynamic aspect of position or status if that person carries out his rights and obligations in accordance with his position. The difference between position and role is based on the interests of science. These elements cannot be separated because they are interrelated and depend on each other. There cannot be a role if there is no position, and there will also be no position without a role. Each character has various roles originating from the patterns of the environment he occupies. have the power to shape the role of a person or organization depending on the problem to be solved or overcome. The term "role" is adopted from a term known in the world of theater. In the world of theater, a person who plays must be able to carry out an activity or explore the characteristics of a certain character. In his position as a character, he is required to be able to behave exactly the same as the character he plays. individual actions as social actors. Every organization that wants to achieve a certain goal is effectively determined by the behavior of humans who work together in the organization as well as the behavior of a person as an individual in a group that joins and is related to the organization. Management plays a strategic role to improve performance and the achievement of effective goals. Human behavior in organizational collaboration is the study of the field of science known as organizational behavior, which discusses organizational behavior, multidisciplinary approaches, organizational performance effectiveness, opportunities and organizational challenges, and organizational behavior models. (Benhard Tewal et al.: 2017).

Illegal Fishing and Management of Natural Resources

Illegal fishing is defined as any fishing activity that is prohibited by the applicable regulations. This operation is illegal since all ship activities are not disclosed to the authorized fishery institution or agency, generating suspicions that the fishing activity is illegal, dangerous, and may result in losses due to noncompliance. The presence of restrictions on the use of marine products causes losses to both the regional economy and the sustainability of the region's marine ecology. official) and catching fish is synonymous with fishing. So, in general, illegal fishing is defined as taking, fishing, and fishing unlawfully (Hasibuan: 2021).

Illegal fishing poses a major threat to marine security and has a significant impact on both the state and residents, particularly those who make a living as fishermen. Illegal fishing

activities create significant losses since people who fish do not follow existing restrictions, resulting in depleted fish stocks at sea. fast reduced and imbalanced with the time of the fish's growth and development This practice is carried out by parties who have no concern for the evolution of marine ecosystems and just seek to maximize profit without considering the long-term negative implications. As a result, fishing must be carried out in accordance with the provisions of regulations and laws that have been regulated in order for the ecosystem's sustainability and long-term viability to have a positive impact on the fishermen's economy.

Given that natural resources provide a reliable contribution to economic growth and sources of foreign exchange as well as development capital for Indonesia, it can be stated that natural resources have played an important role in the Indonesian economy in the past, present, and future, and that its application must consider what has been agreed upon internationally. However, while natural resources contribute significantly to development, the sustainability of their availability is frequently ignored, and the rules that should be followed as the basis for carrying out the management of a business and/or activity supporting the development of the economic sector are not given much attention, resulting in a tendency for a decrease in power consumption to support the environment and the dwindling of natural resources (Nurlinda, 2017).

Natural resource and environmental management that is not carried out in accordance with their carrying capacity can result in food, water, energy, and environmental crises. In general, practically all forms of natural resources and environmental components in Indonesia undergo a loss in quality and quantity from time to time (Ramadhani & Ekaviana, 2020). Environmental management in the era of Regional Autonomy still refers to Law No. 23 of 1997 about Environmental Management, as well as Law No. 32 of 2004 concerning Regional Government and Law No. 33 of 2004 concerning the Balance of Central Finance and Area. Its power is governed by Government Regulation No. 25 of 2000, which governs Government Authorities and Provincial Authorities as Autonomous Regions. The Provincial Government has six functions in environmental management, particularly in dealing with districts/cities, hence the emphasis on environmental management is in the districts/cities. There are 79 Authorities in the environmental field included in the circular letter of the Minister of Home Affairs No. 045/560 dated May 24, 2002, addressing the recognition of Authorities/Positive Lists. In the implementation of sustainable national development, the Natural Resources and Environment sector must pay attention to the further elaboration of the mandate contained in the National Development Program, which is essentially an effort to use natural resources as

much as possible for the prosperity of the people while considering the preservation of environmental functions and balance (Paramita et al., 2018). The World Summit on Sustainable Development (WSSD) in Johannesburg in 2002, Indonesia was active in discussing and attempting to overcome the decline in environmental quality, and it was decided to carry out sustainable development for the welfare of present and future generations based on developing a balanced economy, social culture, and environment as pillars that rely on and strengthen one another. Sustainable development is defined as development that serves the requirements of the present without jeopardizing the right of future generations to meet their own needs. Sustainable development entails ensuring the quality of human existence while not exceeding the capacity of the ecosystem to support it (Thacker et al., 2019). Thus, the concept of sustainable development is designed to meet the requirements of the present without jeopardizing future generations' ability to meet their own needs. This notion consists of two parts: (a) The first is the need, particularly the basic needs of disadvantaged groups of people, which must be prioritized by all countries; (b) the second is the limitation. Technological expertise and social organization must consider the environment's limited ability to support current and future human requirements.

B. Methods

This study is using qualitative approach. In general, qualitative research seeks to comprehend what is symbolized in people's behavior from the perspective of the community itself, and it is characterized as scientific study that is founded on the foundation of hypotheses created via research and controlled empirically. Qualitative research not only offers data as it is, but also attempts to interpret correlations as existing and applicable characteristics such as point of view or continuing process. Meanwhile, Lexy J. Moleong's research method is built on the research foundation, research paradigm, problem formulation, research stages, research procedures, criteria, and techniques for reviewing data analysis, and data interpretation. The researcher uses qualitative research methodologies to complete this study, which emphasizes the meaning and process of an activity rather than the results of an activity. According to Lexy J. Moleong's book *Qualitative Research Methodology 2016*, the authors consider using qualitative research, such as:

1. When working with several statements, it is easier to adapt qualitative methodologies.
2. This strategy implies the nature of the researcher-respondent interaction indirectly.

3. This strategy is more sensitive and responds to the management of joint influence on the patterns being confronted.

Furthermore, the researcher employs a descriptive approach in completing this research, which means that the data collected is a collection of data derived from manuscripts, interviews, field notes, personal documents or notes of researcher memos, and official documents that play a role in supporting research (Sugiyono, 2016).

C. Results and Discussion

The Marine and Fishery Resources Supervision Base has the duties and functions to carry out what is mandated in the Minister of Marine Affairs and Fisheries Decree Number: PER.33/PERMEN-KP/2016 concerning the organization and Technical Implementation Unit (UPT) of the Resource Supervision Base Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (PSDKP), such:

1. To develop a strategic work plan (renkestra), programs, and evaluations in the field of marine and fishery resource monitoring.
2. Monitor marine and fishery resources for behaviors that are harmful to the Indonesian sea.
3. Establishing a community supervisory group (POKMASWAS)
4. Implement and assess the management of marine and fisheries resource infractions
5. Manage operational implementation and logistical planning for marine and fishery resource monitoring activities.
6. Establish and maintain supervisory facilities and infrastructure.
7. Carry out supervisory vessel supervision planning and growth.
8. In addition to carrying out administrative and domestic management of marine and fishery resource supervision bases.

One of the roles of the Marine and Fisheries Resource Base (PSDKP) is to empower the community in supervising illicit fishing. First, the researcher will discuss a number of interviews linked to illicit fishing in general. In 2009, to be specific, in article 9 paragraph 1, it is stated that everyone is prohibited from owning, controlling, carrying, or using fishing gear that destroys the sustainability of fish resources in the Indonesian State Fisheries Management Area, or can be abbreviated as illegal fishing is an activity or effort carried out in catching fish but using fishing gear that is not environmentally friendly, as conveyed by Mr. Muslani as the head of the General Sub-Section at the time.

As a result, the Marine and Fisheries Resource Base supervises and enforces rules that regulate illegal fishing activities, but due to a limited number of supervisory personnel and infrastructure, such as supervisory vessels, the supervision of illegal fishing activities must involve the community, particularly fishermen who see the sea as a source of income. their livelihoods and consider the long-term consequences of illicit fishing The implementation of supervising community group development is one of the key tasks and functions of the Marine and Fisheries Supervision Base (POKMASWAS). Indonesia has been acknowledged as a country with a wide and diverse natural resource base, spanning from renewable to non-renewable resources. These natural resources become a big capital, requiring careful management and monitoring, particularly the sea as a source of energy. locations physically next to other countries, making them prone to triggering difficulties and having a high possibility for resources to be grabbed without regard for long-term hazards by outsiders at state borders Based on the regulation of the Minister of Marine Affairs and Fisheries, who pioneered the formation of the Marine and Fishery Resources Supervision Base (PSDKP): Number: 69/KEPMEN-KP/2020 concerning the organization and work procedures of the technical implementing unit for marine and fishery resource supervision. The Head of the Base is a structural position of echelon III, and the Head of the Administrative Sub-section, the Head of the Facilities and Infrastructure Section, the Head of the Supervision and Violation Handling Section, and the Functional Position Group are all below.

Input

Input is an input or things that are needed in creating a step towards achieving the goals to be achieved by an organization, group of people or agencies that have an orientation in the process of expected results. Notes such as the amount of funds needed, the number of employees or adequate participants, good infrastructure support and the existence of a sufficient amount of time in the implementation of the process.

According to what was conveyed by Mr. Muhamad Syamsu Rokhman as the Judicial Supervision and Handling Section on Thursday, June 9, 2022, which stated that:

“...This Pokmaswas activity is organized by the PSDKP on a scale by providing the community with training and understanding about the adverse effects of illegal fishing activities, both from the short term to the long term as well as providing education to the community, especially fishermen that certain types of fishing gear have the potential to damage biota. the sea and cause a lot of losses which have a huge impact on the economy of the fishing community...”

Supported by the statement of Mr. Salman Mokoginta as Head of the Marine and Fisheries Resources Base on June 10, 2022 which said that:

“...This pokmaswas activity is a representative activity of the government's seriousness in responding to long-term marine product management and maintaining the economic stability of the community by forming a community group that has concern for many aspects of losses due to illegal fishing...”

However, it was also conveyed by Mr. Salman Mokoginta as Head of the Marine and Fisheries Resources Base on June 10, 2022 which became a note:

”...Our efforts are not only educating people on the mainland, but also empowering fishing communities to report suspicions of actions suspected of committing violations such as illegal fishing, but only reporting to the PSDKP because if the community immediately moves to the ships The suspicious people are worried that unwanted things will happen. The main reason for involving the community in this case is limited time, members and infrastructure such as the number of ships and crew. Then with the cooperation of the community who have the awareness to take care of their property in the form of the fishermen's livelihood, it becomes a very effective step to do...”

Output

Output is something that is produced and the provisions obtained in the process of producing certain services and achievements. Output becomes a benchmark for the success of the inputs that have been processed, so that in it there is a study that contains things that have been successfully carried out and obtained in the mission and vision of an organization. or agencies that have a goal orientation that they want to achieve maximally. Where this output is assessed as the result of the process of implementing the goals that have been set, as conveyed by Mr. Muhamad Syamsu Rokhman as the Judicial Supervision and Handling Section on Thursday, June 9, 2022 who said that :

“...By involving the community in monitoring illegal fishing, we have additional human resources voluntarily because of the full awareness of the community itself and this is proven by the inclusion of various reports from people who are active at sea and seeing indications of suspicion on ships carrying out illegal fishing activities. or other illegal things. This is a good progress for the POKMASWAS program that we are holding...”

Outcome is a level of quality and productivity produced, as stated in a previous interview that this POKMASWAS activity is considered sufficient to help the work of PSDKP in its main tasks, one of which is eradicating illegal fishing. as explained by Mr. Johari as Head of the Supervision and Handling Violation Section. Supervise marine and fishery resources, and develop community supervisory groups (Pokmawas).

"...With human resources that are part of the supervisory fleet and the number of available ships is still undervalued when compared to the vastness of the oceans and borders that must be monitored at all times, you can imagine when the officers have sailed to the east while the perpetrators have just started their activities in the west so it is not on time. to find them, it is different with fishermen who are quite a lot and scattered everywhere and always move in the sea alternately, of course they are more frequent and the rate of finding illegal fishing vessels is easier. This is the reference that the reports from fishermen are form of a positive outcome..."

It is the advantage of a policy that can be seen from the level of community participation and the level of community satisfaction, this can be seen from the high awareness of the community in providing reports regarding the existence of ships suspected of carrying out illegal fishing activities. Reports are received in the form of whatsapp, email even local residents contacted the PSDKP headquarters directly by coming directly to the nearest PSDKP office. As has been discussed above, this is also reinforced by the statement of Ibu Ayu as Secretary to the General Chairperson of PSDKP that:

"...'We received reports from the public asking us to go to the field or the location of the ship that was worried about carrying out illegal activities, together with the community we checked the details of the situation and ascertained whether it was true that the ship was illegal and committed a violation, and also several times we met the crew ships originating from abroad besides committing violations, they also cannot use Indonesian even though they are in Indonesian waters coupled with illegal actions, then PSDKP while thanking the community for participation also immediately takes legal action that has been determined..."

It is the impact of increasing community welfare and community income. Which can be seen if the fish caught are in accordance with the rules, then the profit is of course in favor of the community this is due to the characteristics of PSDKP which incidentally is the local government, of course, is a purely non-profit institution that responsible for the economic and social fields. With the preservation of the sea and all marine life, it can be utilized as well as possible for the needs of people's lives. As stated by Mr. Syamsu as the general chairman that:

"...We are committed to serving the community in our field so that apart from focusing on monitoring illegal activities such as illegal fishing and so on, we also control the supply of fish in our waters using statistics. So in the end the results of all of that are returned for the welfare of the community..."

D. Conclusion

Essentially, the PSDKP program is focused on monitoring illegal activities, controlling the supply of fish in the sea, and providing space for the population to live. POKMASWAS is a PSDKP program that aims to make communities legitimate in order to reduce and eliminate

illegal fishing. So, in the end, the outcomes of all of that are returned for the community's benefit. As a result, the Marine and Fishery Resources Supervision Base (PSDKP) has several tasks and functions as mandated, namely preparing a strategic work plan (renkestra), supervising marine and fishery resources, providing group guidance to the supervisory community (POKMASWAS), evaluating the handling of marine and fishery resource violations, carrying out operations and preparation of facilities and infrastructure, maintaining supervision facilities and infrastructure.

E. References

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